

FRACTURE BEHAVIOR OF CFRP REINFORCED CONCRETE

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SUMMARY: Since carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRPs) has excellent mechanical properties such as high specific strength and modulus, they have been used as light-weight structural materials for aerospace vehicle, automobiles and so on. Recently, CFRPs have been applied to architectures and infrastructures as materials for repair and reinforcement. In the present paper, mechanical properties of CFRP reinforced concrete (CFRPRC) were evaluated and its fracture behavior was characterized. First, compressive and flexural tests of CFRPRC were conducted to investigate the effect of size and content of CFRP pieces on compressive and flexural strength and work of fracture. Next, fracture surfaces were observed with a videomicroscope to understand the mechanism of reinforcement. Flexural strength increases and compressive strength slightly increases with increasing CFRP content. In the load-displacement curves in the flexural tests for the specimens reinforced with CFRP pieces, large displacement is observed after maximum load. As a result, work of fracture of these specimens is much higher than that of the specimen without CFRP pieces. It is concluded that addition of CFRP pieces to concrete improves the flexural strength and work of fracture due to bridging effect.

KEYWORDS: CFRP, recycle, concrete, compressive, flexural

INTRODUCTION

Since carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRPs) has excellent mechanical properties such as high specific strength and modulus, they have been used as light-weight structural materials for aerospace vehicle, automobiles and so on. Recently, CFRPs have been applied to architectures and infrastructures as materials for repair and reinforcement and a lot of work has been conducted on CFRP/concrete structures [1-9]. Cement reinforced with short carbon fiber has been experimentally investigated by Chung [10]. In these cases, the mechanical properties of the reinforced or repaired materials have been improved. However, the materials are not cost-effective because virgin CFRPs or carbon fibers have been used.

On the other hand, CFRP is difficult to be recycled because of its hardness and chemical stability. Generally speaking, recycling methods are classified into three categories; material recycling, chemical recycling and thermal recycling. In material recycling, wasted CFRPs are directly utilized through mixture with base material. Toray has recently developed crushing and classification technique of CFRP wastes in their project. At the next stage, we are trying to develop new materials using crushed CFRPs. One of them is CFRP reinforced concrete (CFRPRC).

A project to establish the recycling system of glass fiber reinforced plastics (GFRPs) was conducted by Government Industrial Research Institutes (GIRIS, former AIST) in Japan ten years ago[11]. As material recycling in this project, a device to cut large scale GFRP wastes such as boats was developed and also some concrete materials mixed with crushed GFRP were fabricated. A private company has recently developed Alkali-resistant glass fiber (AGF) reinforced concrete (so called GRC) and put it on the market. Mechanical properties of GRC are better than conventional concrete. More recently,

polymer mortars containing wasted polymer has been investigated by Bignozzi et al. [12]. However, recycled CFRP has never been utilized to reinforce concrete materials.

The CFRPRC is expected to have excellent mechanical properties since the CFRP pieces show good adhesion to concrete and they can be dispersed in concrete better than carbon fibers as reinforcement. From the chemical point of view, CFRP is resistant to alkali-aggregate reaction. In addition, wasted and crushed CFRP is less expensive than the virgin AGF.

In the present paper, mechanical properties of CFRPRC were evaluated and its fracture behavior was characterized. First, compressive and flexural tests of CFRPRC were conducted to investigate the effect of content and size of CFRP pieces on compressive and flexural strength and work of fracture. The effect of specimen size on those properties is also discussed. Next, fracture surfaces were observed with a videomicroscope to understand the fracture mechanism of this material.

EXPERIMENTAL

Figure 1 shows the crashed CFRP pieces with small (S), medium (M) and large (L) size. Average sizes of these CFRP pieces are 3.4*0.4, 9.9*2.2 and 21*7.7 mm² for S-, M- and L-size, respectively. Their thickness varies between 0.05 and 0.2 mm. Table 1 summarizes mixture ratios of CFRPRC. For all kinds of mixture, water to cement ratio and coarse aggregate (including CFRP) to cement ratio are

Table 1 Mixture ratios (in weight) of CFRPRC. CFRP/C, W/C and A/C denote CFRP, water and aggregate to cement ratios, respectively.

	A	B	C	D
CFRP/C	0.00	0.05	0.075	0.10
W/C	0.45	0.45	0.45	0.45
A/C	4.35	4.32	4.30	4.28
□fine□	(2.27)	(2.22)	(2.20)	(2.18)
(coarse)	(2.08)	(2.09)	(2.10)	(2.10)

Table 2 Specimen sizes for the compressive and flexural tests (unit [mm]).

	Compressive		Width	Flexural	
	diameter	Length		Height	Length
Large	100	200	100	100	400
Small	50	100	40	40	160

(a) S-size

(b) M-size

(c) L-size

Fig. 1 Crushed CFRP pieces used for reinforcement.

kept constant 0.45 and 2.1, respectively. A normal type of melaminesulfonic acid agent was used to ensure the workability. For the mixture B, C, and D, the S-, M- and L-sized CFRP pieces were used. Thus, there are ten kinds of mixture in all. After mixing all the constituent materials, slump values were measured to investigate workability of fresh concrete. As this value becomes small, viscosity becomes large and workability becomes bad. Circular and square rods were fabricated for compressive and flexural tests, respectively, according to JIS standards for concrete and mortar materials (Table 2). Thus, the large and small specimens were made for the above ten kinds of mixture.

The mechanical tests were conducted on the 14th day after the fabrication. The compressive tests were conducted using a normal testing machine for concrete. The flexural tests were performed using both the standard testing machine and electrohydraulic testing machine with the aid of a three-point flexural

test jig at a crosshead speed of 1.0 mm/min to obtain the load-displacement curves. Because the specimens B, C and D show ductile load-displacement curves after fracture, measurement was stopped at load of 200 N after fracture. Work of fracture was calculated as the integral of the load-displacement curves in the flexural tests.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 3 summarizes the experimental results of the slump tests. The slump value largely decreases with increasing CFRP content, which means that the fresh concrete becomes harder. This problem can be easily solved if we use the polycarboxylic acid agent, which improves fluidity remarkably. The compressive and flexural strength is shown in Figure 2 (a) and (b), respectively. The solid and dotted lines denote the large and small specimens, respectively. The compressive strength slightly increases with increasing CFRP content for the Large_M, Large_S and Small_S specimens while the compressive strength of the Small_L and Large_L specimens is lower than that of the blank material without CFRP pieces. The flexural strength of the large specimens increases approximately linearly

Table 3 Slump values of fresh CFRPRC (unit [cm]).

CFRP size	A	B	C	D
Nothing	15.5	-	-	-
L	-	7	5.8	2.5
M	-	5.8	4	2.3
S	-	7.2	4.8	1.6

Fig. 2 Effect of content and size of CFRP pieces on (a) compressive and (b) flexural strength of the large and small specimens.

(a) B (5 %) (b) C (7.5 %) (c) D (10 %)

Fig.3 Effect of the size ratio on the compressive strength. The solid and hollow plots denote the large and small specimens, respectively.

Fig.4 Effect of the size ratio on the flexural strength. The solid and hollow plots denote the large and small specimens, respectively.

with increasing CFRP content while the strengthening effect is obscure in the small specimens though its strength is higher than that of the large specimens. The reason why the strength in the small specimens and the specimens reinforced with L-sized CFRP pieces is not improved evidently, is supposed to be the “size effect”. Figures 3 and 4 show the effect of the size ratio of CFRP pieces to specimen, denoted by R , on the compressive and flexural strength, respectively, normalized by the average strength of the specimen A (0 %). As the value of R becomes small, which means the size of CFRP pieces is small and/or the specimen size is large, the normalized strength increases because the dispersion of the CFRP pieces is regarded to be homogeneous. In this case, the strength increment is approximately proportional to the CFRP content. The scatter of strength in the small specimens is large than that in the large specimens. In the small specimens with the relatively large value of R , the strength tends to depend on the local distribution of the CFRP pieces, especially in the flexural tests, because the number of the CFRP pieces involved in the specimen is limited. Then, the strength of the Small_L and Small_M specimens sometimes becomes lower than that of the blank specimens.

Figure 5 (a) shows the typical load-displacement curves in the flexural tests for the small specimens with the M-sized CFRP pieces. In the specimen A (0 %), the load drops sharply after the maximum load at which fracture starts. On the other hand, in the specimens B (5 %), C (7.5 %) and D (10 %) reinforced with CFRP pieces, the load gradually decreases, resulting in large displacement after the maximum load. Figure 5 (b) shows the average values of work of fracture obtained from the load-

(a)

(b)

Fig.5 Load-displacement curves ((a)) and work of fracture ((b)) in the flexural tests of CFRPRC.

Fig. 6 Fracture behavior of a CFRPC specimen. Fig. 7 CFRP piece bridging a crack.

displacement curves in the flexural tests. Work of fracture of the specimens B, C and D are much higher than that of the specimen A (Fig. 3 (b)). It is interesting that the specimens reinforced with L-sized CFRP shows the highest work of fracture although their flexural strength is not always the highest (dotted lines with the circle plots in Fig. 2 (b)).

Figure 6 shows a small specimen B reinforced with the M-sized CFRP pieces after the fracture in the flexural test. This specimen bears the load more than 200 N with large deflection even after the maximum load, not being separated into two pieces. Figure 7 shows a CFRP piece which has a role of bridging a crack in concrete. This bridging leads to improvement of flexural strength and work of fracture. It is expected that this ductile fracture behavior provides seismic capacity for concrete structures using CFRPRC.

CONCLUDING REMARK

Fracture behavior of concrete reinforced with recycled CFRP pieces is investigated. Addition of CFRP pieces to concrete improves the compressive and flexural strength as well as work of fracture. The strength depends on the size ratio of CFRP pieces to specimen. In the large specimens or the specimens reinforced with the S- or M-sized CFRP pieces, the strength increases with increasing content of CFRP pieces. Improvement of work of fracture results from crack bridging by the CFRP pieces. However, further investigation is needed to optimize the size and content of CFRP pieces.

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